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Evaluation of quality characteristics of soy based millet biscuits

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ABSTRACT

Soy based biscuits were developed by incorporation of millet (kodo and kutki) flour at 70, 80, 90 and 100% level for increasing protein content of biscuit and utilization of millet. When millet flour was fortified with soy flour it gives high level of protein of 11.88% of biscuit for 70% kodo flour incorporation, it was much higher than that of 5.09% for control biscuits. Fat content increased from 11.98% for control biscuits to 14.82 % for 100% kodo incorporation soy based kodo biscuits. Protein and fat values of kutki biscuits is slightly higher than the kodo biscuits; its protein value was 12.07% for 70% incorporation to soy based kutki biscuits, much higher than the 5.3% for control biscuits. Fat content is increased with increasing incorporation level of kutki flour from 12.08% for control biscuits to 15.18% for 100% soy based kutki biscuits. The sensory analysis indicated that the 70% kodo and 90% kutki biscuits were the best on the basis of overall acceptability on the 9- point hedonic scale. Effect of incorporation level of millet flour in soy based biscuit on the physical characteristics such as spread ratio, % spread factor, weight, density and moisture content increased whereas diameter, thickness, volumetric expansion ratio and volume decreased with increasing incorporation level of millet flour. As the level of substitution of millet flour increases the yellowness index decreases and whiteness index increases for soy fortified kodo biscuits whereas yellowness index increases and whiteness index decreases for soy fortified kutki biscuits. Cutting force increased whereas firmness decreased due to incorporation of millet flour.

Key words : Millet, soy based millet biscuit, kutki, kodo.

INTRODUCTION

Bakery industry is the one of the largest food industries in India with an annual turnover of about 3000 billion. The biscuit industry has been growing at an average rate of 15% during the past 3 years and this is expected to be maintained in coming years [IBMA, 2010]. Breads and biscuits

are major products accounting for 80% of the total bakery products in India. The contributing factor about this is urbanization resulting in increased demand for ready to eat convenient products like breads and biscuits. Among convenience foods biscuits are very convenient and inexpensive but have only about 6 to 7% protein [Agarwal, 1990]. Its popularity is due to availability of varieties of products having different taste and texture profiles at reasonable cost with longer self life. Now days there is an ever-growing demand for high protein biscuits. This may be achieved through incorporation of protein-rich ingredients from soybean and use of millet flour [Waters 1978; Dubois and Hoover 1981]. Diets mainly contain cereal/millet based food products and contain only small amount of protective and recovering protein.

Soybean is an excellent health food and it contains 40% good quality protein, 23% carbohydrates, 20% cholesterol free oil and sufficient amounts of minerals and vitamins. Amino acid profile of soy protein is excellent amongst plant proteins. Hence, it is superior to other plant proteins as it contains most of the essential amino acids except methionine, which is abundant in cereals, and it is most economical source of dietary protein.

Soybean can be effectively utilized as protein food in a number of ways. To find additional food products with better nutrition is the prime need of the nation. Millets and soybean can very well fit into the food chain for this purpose. Food consumption of people in any part of the world is related to agro-ecological condition, socio-cultural factors, religions and to the need of proper nutrition.

Millets contain about 8% protein and 4% fat. They are rich source of vitamins and minerals. Millets are especially rich in calcium. The dietary carbohydrates content of millets is also relatively high. Starch is the main carbohydrate component and they contain a higher proportion of non-starchy polysaccharides (dietary fiber) also. Prolamines and glutelins form the major portion of their proteins. The fats from millets contain a higher portion of unsaturated fatty acids and supply essential fatty acids. Although, a considerable portion of nutrients is concentrated in the seed coat, the bioavailability of the nutrients present in the endosperm is higher than the seed coat nutrients. Anti nutritional factors such as phytate and polyphenols are also present in millets but they are mostly confined to the seed coat and the milled millets are generally free from the antinutritional factors. Kodo millet (*Paspalum serobicultum*) and Kutki (*Panicum miliare*) are minor millets have certain specialties, which, if exploited, may yield products of superior nutritional and technological characteristics than the major cereals, but their utilization is limited.

They have remained as the food for the people of the lower socio-economic strata and traditional consumers, because of their coarse texture, characteristic flavor, intense colored seed coat and cultural attachments. With constantly increasing awareness of good nutrition for healthy living, the consumption of millets is increasing. They are considered poor man's diet and a very little work has been done on development of value added products to increase their utilization. Preparation of biscuit from millets and its supplementation with soy-flour will result in increased utilization of millet and production of nutritious biscuits. In view of this consideration the present work was under taken to study the quality characteristics of soy protein enriched millet biscuits for its physical, nutritional, sensory and properties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of raw materials

Kodo and kutki millets were obtained through M.P. Vigyan Sabha from Patalkot area, Bhopal. These millets were dehusked and milled for getting flour. The blanched soybean was dried in a tray and the dried soy-dal was milled in a burr mill at SPU Centre, CIAE, Bhopal. All materials and ingredients purchased from local market. Cleaning of kodo and kutki millets was done by washing with water followed by drying, as these contained smaller mud particles. For dehusking of millet a domestic grain mill was used. Same mill was used for grinding of millet into flour by changing of sieve.

Product development

Soy based millet biscuits were prepared using the traditional creamy method [Sinha and Kulkarni, 1991]. Biscuits were prepared from the blends containing 30% (bakers) full fat soy flour and substitute refined wheat flour with 70%, 80%, 90%, 100% millet flour. The process for production of soy fortified millet biscuit consisted of creaming of sugar, salt, ammonium bicarbonate, baking soda and shortenings. All the ingredients were weighed accurately by balance. Creaming was followed by addition of water and soy flour, wheat flour or millet flour according to formulation. The dough rolled into uniform sheet of desired thickness and was cut with the help of properly shaped cutter. These biscuits were put in the tray on butter paper and baked in baking oven at 200°C. Baked biscuits were finally cooled and evaluated for baking and nutritional properties.

Proximate composition of raw material developed products

The samples were analyzed for protein; fat, moisture content, carbohydrate and ash content using standard [AOAC, 1984] method.

Physical properties of soy millet based biscuits

Diameter, thickness spread ratio, percent spread factor, volume and density of biscuits were calculated as per the method described by [AACC, 1967].

Sensory evaluation

Biscuit were evaluated organoleptically for different quality attributes and overall acceptability. Sensory evaluation was performed using a panel consisting 9 untrained panelists. The ratings were done on a 9-point Hedonic scale. The mean of sensory scores for attributes *viz.* colour, flavour, taste and smell / odor and overall acceptability were recorded.

Colour of soy based millet biscuits

Colour of biscuit was measured using the Hunter Lab Colorimeter. The instrument was standardized each time with a white and a black ceramic plate.

Texture analysis of soy based millet biscuits

Texture analysis of soy based millet biscuits were done by Texture Analyzer (Make Stable Micro System, U.K, Model TA -XT2). Texture analysis of biscuits was done by two methods (TA and TPA test). TA test was done for measuring cutting force of biscuits and TPA test for firmness, cohesiveness and springiness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data on proximate composition of millet (kodo & kutki) flour, refined wheat flour and full fat soy flour have been given in Table 1. It was observed that the fat content of full fat soy flour is four times that of kodo and kutki flour. Similarly the protein content of full fat soy flour is about five times that of kodo and kutki flour. This indicated suitability of supplementation of millet flour with full fat soy flour [Arora and Srivastva, 2002].

Table 1: Proximate composition of kodo & kutki, refined wheat flour and full fat soy flour

S.No.	Constituents (%)	Kodo flour	Kutki flour	Refined wheat flour	Full fat soy flour
1.	Moisture content	6.77	7.69	14.3	8.01
2.	Protein content	7.88	8.29	10.20	42.10
3.	Fat content	4.90	5.10	0.90	20.05
4.	Ash content	4.10	5.40	0.80	6.60
5.	Carbohydrate content	76.45	73.52	73.8	23.24

Effect of incorporation of millet (kodo and kutki) flour on physical properties of soy based millet (kodo and kutki) biscuit

It was observed that the spread ratio increased with increasing level of millet flour. This may be due to the fact that the thickness of the biscuit less than control biscuits after baking. It may be possible due to coarsely ground flour had better spreading properties than the finely ground flour.

Effect of incorporation of kodo flour on physical properties of soy based millet biscuit

The effect of level of incorporation of kodo flour on physical properties of biscuit such as weight, diameter, thickness, volume, density and volumetric expansion ratio (VER) was studied and given in Table 2. It was observed that with increasing level of kodo flour, diameter, thickness and volumetric expansion ratio of biscuits decreased, whereas percent spread factor, spread ratio, weight and density increased. It was observed that the with increasing level of incorporation of millet flour, thickness decreased from 5.45 mm for 70% to 5.1 mm for 100%, but density increased from 0.66 (g/cm³) for 70% to 0.72 (g/cm³) for 100% kodo biscuit, whereas VER was decreased form 1.59 for control and from 1.51 for 70% to 1.49 for 100% kodo biscuits.

Table 2: Effect of incorporation of kodo flour on physical properties of soy based kodo biscuit

S. No.	Parameters	Levels of incorporation of kodo flour				
		Control	70 %	80%	90%	100%
1	Weights (gm)	6.70	6.58	6.72	6.80	6.98
2	Diameter (mm)	50.16	49.20	49.20	49.19	49.20
3	Thickness (mm)	5.45	5.16	5.15	5.18	5.10
4	Spread ratio	9.03	9.53	9.55	9.15	9.48
5	% of S. Factor	100.00	105.54	105.76	101.39	104.98
6	Volume (cm ³)	10.36	9.81	9.79	10.03	9.69
7	Density (g/cm ³)	0.65	0.66	0.69	0.68	0.72
8	VER	1.59	1.51	1.50	1.54	1.49

Effect of incorporation of kutki flour on physical properties of soy based kutki biscuits

The effect of incorporation of kutki flour on physical properties of biscuits such as weight, diameter, thickness, volume, density and VER was studied and data has been tabulated in Table 3. It was observed that with increasing level of incorporation of kutki flour diameter, thickness, volume and volumetric expansion ratio decreased, whereas spread ratio, % spread factor, and density increased.

Table 3: Effect of incorporation of kutki flour on physical properties of soy based kutki biscuit

S.No	Parameters	Levels of incorporation of Kutki flour				
		Control	70 %	80%	90%	100%
1	Weight (gm)	9.85	9.88	9.90	10.01	10.12
2	Diameter (cm)	50.25	50.18	50.15	50.1	49.76
3	Thickness (cm)	8.06	6.94	6.90	6.83	6.49
4	Spread ratio	6.23	7.25	7.27	7.34	7.67
5	% of S. Factor	100.00	116.37	116.69	117.84	123.11
6	Volume (cm ³)	15.95	13.79	13.62	13.46	12.61
7	Density (g/cm ³)	0.62	0.72	0.75	0.74	0.80
8	VER	2.05	1.76	1.74	1.72	1.55

Effect of incorporation of black variety of kutki flour on physical properties of soy based kutki biscuit

The effect of incorporation of black variety kutki flour on physical properties of biscuit such as diameter, thickness, volume, density, weight and VER was studied and given in Table 4. From the table, it was observed that with increasing level of incorporation of black kutki flour, diameter, thickness and VER decreased whereas spread ratio, percent spread factor, density and weight increased. The data indicated that the with increasing level of incorporation of black kutki flour from control to 100%, the diameter decreased from 49.22 mm for control, to 49.21 mm for 70% black kutki biscuit and 49.19 mm for 100% black kutki. Density of the biscuit increased from 0.57 (g/cm³) for control and from 0.74(g/cm³) for 70% kutki biscuit to 0.80 (g/cm³) for 100% incorporation of black kutki flour. Volumetric expansion ratio decreased form 1.57 for control and from 1.34 for 70% to 1.29 for 100% kutki biscuits.

Table 4. Effect of incorporation of black variety kutki flour on physical properties of soy based kutki biscuit

S. No	Parameters	Levels of black variety kutki flour				
		Control	70 %	80%	90%	100%
1	Weight (gm)	9.05	9.57	9.58	9.91	9.99
2	Diameter (mm)	49.22	49.21	49.20	49.21	49.19
3	Thickness (mm)	7.99	6.79	6.61	6.62	6.56
4	Spread ratio	6.16	7.25	7.44	7.43	7.5
5	% S. Factor	100	117.7	120.78	120.62	121.75
6	Volume (cm ³)	15.19	12.9	12.56	12.58	12.46
7	Density (g/cm ³)	0.57	0.74	0.76	0.70	0.80
8	VER	1.57	1.34	1.3	1.30	1.29

Effect of incorporation of millet flour on moisture content of soy based (kodo & kutki) millet biscuits

The effect of incorporation of millet flour on moisture content of soy based biscuits was studied and data are tabulated in Table 5. It was observed that moisture content remained below 4% for all level of incorporation of millet flour. The data showed that no significant effect on moisture content was observed due to incorporation of millet.

Table 5: Effect of millet flour incorporation on moisture content of soy based millet (kodo & kutki) biscuits

S. No.	Sample	Moisture content (%)
1	Control	3.26
2	Kodo 70%	3.93
3	Kodo 80%	3.94
4	Kodo 90%	4.2
5	Kodo 100%	3.97
6	Kutki 70%	3.43
7	Kutki 80%	3.72
8	Kutki 90%	3.84
9	Kutki 100%	3.87
10	Kutki black 70%	3.73
11	Kutki black 80%	3.68
12	Kutki black 90%	3.69
13	Kutki black 100	3.81

Effect of level incorporation of millet (kodo & kutki) flour on colour of soy based millet biscuits

Various levels of millets (kodo and Kutki) were tried for substitution in the standard formula of soy fortified biscuits. The level tried were 70%, 80%, 90% and 100% of millets (both black & white varieties) flour. It was found that the Kodo up to 70% & 80 % as replacement to Maida could produce the biscuits with acceptable quality. In case of Kutki up to 100% replacement of Maida produced biscuits of acceptable quality. Colour measurement of soy fortified millet biscuits were carried out by Colour Hunter Lab. Colour differences including visual brightness (ζ), redness to greenness (a), yellowness to blueness (b) of soy fortified millet biscuits were measured by Colour Hunter Lab after standardization with white and black ceramic plate. These values along with yellowness and whiteness index are given in the Table 6 and Table 7. 30% (baker's) full fat soy flour was supplemented in all levels of millet incorporation.

Table 6: Colour attributes of soy based kodo biscuit

Supplementation level	Colour parameters of soy fortified kodo biscuits				
	ζ	A	b	YI	WI
Kodo 70%	47.25	9.80	28.59	60.49	-193.51
Kodo 80%	54.87	6.85	27.24	53.63	-161.05
Kodo 90%	55.09	7.00	26.95	53.14	-158.38
Kodo 100%	54.31	7.13	26.01	52.34	-155.15
Control	62.53	10.26	35.54	60.50	-180.50

Table 7: Color attributes of soy based kutki biscuit

Supplementation Level	Colour parameters of soy fortified kutki biscuits				
	ζ	A	B	YI	WI
kutki 70%	61.64	10.63	34.12	59.31	-175.60
kutki 80%	56.60	12.99	33.27	61.24	-186.24
kutki 90%	52.99	14.01	32.53	62.53	-193.61
kutki 100%	44.36	12.48	27.40	61.00	-193.15
control	62.53	10.26	35.54	60.50	-180.50

Where, ζ : visual brightness; a : redness to greenness; b : yellowness to blueness YI: Yellowness index; WI: Whiteness index.

It was observed from the Table 4.6 & 4.7 that as the level of substitution of millet flour increases the yellowness index decreases and whiteness index increases for soy fortified kodo biscuits whereas yellowness index increases and whiteness index decreases for soy fortified kutki biscuits.

Sensory evaluation soy based kodo biscuits

Sensory attributes such as taste, flavor, color, appearance, texture, and overall acceptability were evaluated on 9-point hedonic scale. The mean scores for these attributes for soy based kodo biscuits are given in Table 8. It was observed that overall acceptability was maximum for 70% kodo biscuit.

Table 8: Mean score of sensory evaluation for soy based kodo biscuits

S. No.	% of kodo flour	Appearance	Color	Flavor	Texture	Taste	Over All Acceptability
1	Control	6.78	6.78	6.56	7.0	6.56	6.89
2	Kodo 70%	5.89	5.67	5.89	6.11	6.33	6.29
3	Kodo 80%	6.09	5.67	5.56	6.09	6.33	6.26
4	Kodo 90%	6.06	5.78	6.0	5.78	5.44	6.20
5	Kodo100%	5.67	5.56	6.0	5.44	5.89	5.64

Sensory evaluation of soy based kutki biscuit

Mean scores of sensory characteristics of kutki biscuits are given in Table 9. The kutki biscuits showed the high acceptability than the kodo biscuit. The mean score of overall acceptability for kodo biscuit is 6.29 for 70% and for kutki 70% it is 6.89 due to its better color and flavor. It was observed that overall acceptability was maximum for 90% kutki biscuit. Similar results were also reported by Zhao, 1996 in case of kutki biscuit.

Table 9: Mean score of sensory evaluation for soy based kutki biscuits

S. No	% of kutki flour	Appearance	Color	Flavor	Texture	Taste	Over All Acceptability
1	control	6.78	6.78	6.56	7.0	6.56	6.87
2	Kutki 70%	6.67	6.78	6.56	6.06	5.94	6.29
3	Kutki80%	6.27	6.50	6.44	6.61	6.33	6.44
4	Kutki 90%	6.72	6.44	6.83	6.64	7.17	7.22
5	Kutki 100%	6.56	6.56	6.44	6.00	6.68	6.68

Texture analysis of soy based millet biscuits

Texture analysis of soy based millet biscuits was done by Texture Analyzer (Make Stable Micro System, U.K. Model TA- XT2). Texture analysis of biscuits was done by two methods (TA and TPA test). TA test was done for measuring cutting force of biscuits and TPA test for firmness, cohesiveness and springiness.

Texture analysis and texture profile analysis of soy based kodo biscuits

The data of texture profile analysis of soy based kodo and kutki biscuits are presented in Table 10 and Table 11 respectively. Cutting force was 28.15 N for control sample and increased to 54.01 N for 80% for Kodo biscuits. In case of Kutki biscuits much cutting force was required then Kodo biscuits. Its value for Kodo 70% was 37.62N and for kutki 70% it is 61.71N. Firmness value of control sample was 63.44 N and for kodo 70% is 30.57N for Kutki it was 54.24N.

Table 10: Texture Analysis and Texture Profile Analysis of soy based Kodo Biscuits

S. No.	Sample	Cutting N	Firmness N	Springiness	Cohesiveness
1	Control	28.15	63.44	1.24	0.94
2	Kodo 70 %	37.62	30.57	1.23	0.094
3	Kodo 80 %	54.01	26.04	0.033	0.002
4	Kodo 90 %	23.96	35.145	0.035	0.002
5	Kodo 100%	33.41	32.83	0.915	0.68

Table 11: Texture Analysis and Texture Profile Analysis test for soy based Kutki biscuits

S. No	Sample	Cutting N	Firmness N	Springiness	Cohesiveness
1	Kutki70%	61.7	54.24	1.34	0.94
2	Kutki80%	62.3	50.27	1.24	0.092
3	Kutki90%	64.1	50.52	1.13	0.012
4	Kutki100	68.4	49.19	1.53	0.003

Table 12: Effect of millet flour level on the baking time of soy based millet biscuits

S. No	Sample	Baking time (min)
1	Control	10
2	Kodo 70%	11
3	Kodo80%	11
4	Kodo90%	12
5	Kodo100%	12
6	Kutki 70%	12
7	Kutki 80%	12
8	Kutki 90%	12
9	Kutki 100%	13
10	Kutki black 70%	13
11	Kutki black 80%	13
12	Kutki black 90%	12
13	Kutki black 100	14

Effect of incorporation of millet flour on baking time of biscuit

Data on the effect of incorporation of millet flour on baking time of biscuit are given in Table 12. Baking time slightly increased due to incorporation of millet flour. Baking time for control sample, kodo 70% and kodo 100% biscuit was 10 min, 11 min and 12 min respectively. Baking time for kutki 70% was 12 min and for kutki 100% it was 13 min and for black kutki it was little more than the kodo and kutki i.e. 13 min for 70% and 14 min for 100%.

The data showed that there are no significant differences observed in baking time of millet incorporated biscuit.

Proximate composition of soy based millet biscuits

The chemical analysis of soy based millet (kodo & kutki) biscuits was done for proximate composition which is discussed below:

Proximate composition of soy based kodo biscuits

The data showed that with increasing level of kodo flour increased the moisture content from 3.26% for control to 3.43% for 70% kodo and 3.87% for 100% kodo biscuits. The results showed that there was increased moisture content of biscuit as increasing level of millet flour. And fat content also increased from 11.98% for control to 14.88% for 100% kodo due to high fat content of kodo flour 4.9% than the wheat flour 0.9% whereas protein content of kodo biscuit decreased from 11.88% for 70% kodo to 11.04 for 100% kodo of soy based kodo biscuits. It was observed from the Table 13 that protein content of soy based millet biscuits was higher than control biscuits. The protein value increased from 5.09% for control biscuit to 11.76% for 70% kodo and 11.04 for 100% soy based kodo biscuit.

Table 13: Proximate composition of soy based kodo biscuits

S. No	Component (%)	Control	70%	80%	90%	100%
1	Moisture	3.26	3.43	3.72	3.84	3.87
2	Fat	11.98	13.13	13.74	14.22	14.82
3	Protein	5.09	11.88	11.76	11.16	11.04

Proximate composition of soy based kutki biscuits

The data on proximate composition of soy based kutki biscuit is given in Table 14.

Table 14: Proximate composition of soy based kutki biscuits

S. No.	Component (%)	Control	70%	80%	90%	100%
1	Moisture	3.26	3.93	3.94	4.2	3.97
2	Fat	12.08	14.52	14.74	15.16	15.18
3	Protein	5.30	12.07	11.94	11.85	11.74

The data showed that the protein content of kutki biscuit is further increased with increasing level of kutki flour from 12.07 for 70% to 11.74 for 100% of soy based kutki biscuits. Fat content increased from 12.08% for control to 15.18% for 100% of soy based kutki biscuits. Moisture content increased with increasing level of kutki flour from 3.26% for control to 3.93% for 70% kutki and 3.97% for 100% soy based kutki biscuits. Protein content of soy based kutki

biscuits increased 5.30% for control to 11.74 for 100% soy based kutki biscuit due to incorporation of full fat soy flour.

CONCLUSION

Efforts have been made to develop soy millet (kodo and kutki) based biscuits by incorporation of millet flour at 70, 80, 90 and 100% level. Proximate composition of soy based millet (kodo & kutki) biscuits, protein content decreased with incorporation of kodo & kutki flour from 11.88% for 70% to 11.04% for 100% soy based kodo biscuits and 12.07% for 70% to 11.74% for 100% soy based kutki biscuits. Fat content increased with increasing level of millet flour. On the basis of physical evaluation density, spread ratio and weight and % spread factor increased whereas diameter, volume and thickness decreased with increasing level incorporation of millet (kodo & kutki) flour. On the basis of sensory evaluation 70% kodo and 90% kutki biscuits were found best.

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